

DL-Mercapto succinic acid as metallochromic indicator for volumetric estimation of copper by sodium thiosulphate

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THE volumetric estimation of copper by thio-sulphate solution is well known. Nowadays EDTA method is widely used for determination of copper ion using indicators such as Eriochrom black-T, Murexide, Pyro catechol violet, Dithiozone, Fast sulphon black F, etc.¹.

The transitional method of estimation of copper by iodometric method using thiosulphate may be replaced by direct titration without using KI.

A solution of copper chloride was prepared by dissolving 6.06 gm $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 250 ml of distilled water. A stock solution of 1% DL-mercapto succinic acid (thiomalic acid BDH Chemical Ltd., England) was prepared dissolving 1% of the substance in 100 ml of distilled water. 0.1M sodium thiosulphate solution was prepared by dissolving 24.821 gm of pure $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH Chemicals, England) in one litre distilled water.

When DL-mercapto succinic acid is added in aqueous solution containing copper ions, violet coloured precipitates are formed. The coloured precipitates are due to formation of metal indicator complex. The estimation of copper may be carried out as follows.

Take 10 ml of copper chloride solution in the conical flask. Add 4-5 drops of DL-mercapto succinic acid as an indicator. Initial colour formed by adding indicator is violet. This is titrated against the standard solution of (0.1M) thiosulphate. A sharp colour change from violet to colourless takes at the end point. The procedure was repeated several times to obtain constant reading. Amount of copper was calculated. The amount of copper obtained by this method was the same as that obtained by standard EDTA titration using Eriochrome black-T as an indicator. The end point shows the proportion of copper to thiosulphate $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ to be 1 : 1.

In the present investigation a method similar to EDTA titration was followed using metal chromic indicator.

New indicator used was DL-mercapto succinic acid

which fulfils all the requirements of metal-chromic indicators.

The stability of the complex with thiosulphate being greater than that of the metal-indicator complex the latter dissociates to a limited extent and during the titration the free metal ions are progressively complexed by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ until the metal ion is completely displaced from metal indicator. Results show that the ratio of copper to $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ is 1 : 1 molar proportion.

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Reference

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Solubility products of Cu(II) and Ag(I) complexes of glycoldimercaptoacetate

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SAXENA and coworkers have made extensive study on the complexing tendencies of several thiols with various metals¹⁻⁵. This communication reports the composition of sparingly soluble complexes of Cu(II) and Ag(I) with glycoldimercaptoacetate by amperometric, pH-metric and conductometric titrations; their equilibrium constants and solubility products by polarographic technique applying Ringbom's method. The changes in the thermodynamic parameters of free energy, enthalpy, entropy accompanying the complexation reactions have also been determined at 30°.

Experimental

Glycoldimercaptoacetate (referred here as GDA) was obtained from Evan's Chemicals, New York and other chemicals were of analar grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation. Conductance and pH were measured respectively with an electronic eye-type conductometer and Cambridge bench pH meter associated with a glass-calomel electrode assembly. A manual polarograph, with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode, was used for amperometric titrations in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 25% ethanol by volume, 0.1M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton X-100 at -0.5 V vs. S.C.E. with h_{eff} value being 38.3 cm :

$$m = 2.963 \text{ mg/sec.}, \quad t = 2.39 \text{ sec.}$$

NOTES

The titrations were performed by usual methods as described earlier⁶ using various concentrations of reactants i.e., metal and ligand, both by direct and reverse processes with each of the reagent alternately used as the titre, and the end points corresponding to the complex formation were obtained from the breaks in the titration curves. The figures have, however, been omitted for the sake of brevity.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behaviour of glycoldimercaptoacetate has already been reported by the authors⁷. For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species, formed during the interaction of metal ion and GDA, a series of amperometric, potentiometric and conductometric titrations were carried out using different concentrations of reactants both by direct (metal ion vs. ligand) and reverse methods. It has been observed that at -0.7 V vs. S.C.E. metals under investigations are reducible but GDA shows inert behaviour. Hence amperometric titrations were performed in $0.1M$ $NaClO_4$ and 0.002% Triton X-100 at -0.7 V. The equivalence points in the titration curves corresponded to the formation of 1 : 1 complex for Cu(II) and 2 : 1 complex for Ag(I).

The values of equilibrium constants for the complexation reactions between metal ion and the ligand have been determined by Ringbom's method⁸. The following equation has been used for evaluating K_t , the conditional or formal equilibrium constant

$$\frac{(i-i_r)(1+rf)}{(i^0-i_r)} = \frac{(1-f) + [(i-f)^2 + 4(1+rf)^2/K_t(C_M^0)^2]^{1/2}}{2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where r is the dilution parameter ($r = C_M^0/C_x$) and f is the titration parameter defined by the equation

$$f = Z \frac{V_x C_x}{V_0 C_M^0} \quad \dots (2)$$

Z being the number of moles of the titre that react with each mole of the titrant; in the present case $Z = 1$ for Cu(II) and 2 for Ag(I). C_M^0 and i^0 are the initial concentration and limiting current of the metal ion respectively; i_r and i are respectively the residual current and the current at any titration point. The titration parameter f becomes equal to 1 at the equivalence point.

When a reducible ion is titrated with an inert one to give a precipitate, the equation (1) at the equivalence point can be written as

$$K_t = \left(\frac{1}{C_M^0} \cdot \frac{i^0 - i_r}{i - i_r} \right)^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

from which the value of K_t under the conditions of the titration can be obtained. The value of $i^0 - i_r$

at the equivalence point was obtained from the plot of

$$\frac{i - i_r}{i^0 - i_r} \cdot \frac{V_0 + V}{V_0} \text{ vs. } f$$

In the absence of any side reaction that could consume either ion, K_t for the precipitation titration is simply the reciprocal of the solubility product, K_s . Thus from the value of K_t , K_s may also be evaluated. The values of K_s for Cu(II) and Ag(I) complexes of glycoldimercaptoacetate at 20° , 30° and 40° are given in Table 1. It is observed that with rise in temperature the value of K_t decreases while that of K_s increases.

TABLE 1. VALUES OF K_s FOR Cu(II) AND Ag(I) COMPLEXES OF GLYCOLDIMERCAPTOACETATE IN 25% ETHANOL, $0.1M$ $NaClO_4$.

Metal complex	Solubility product (K_s)		
	20°	30°	40°
Cu(II)	2.939×10^{-8}	4.797×10^{-8}	6.146×10^{-8}
Ag(I)	3.084×10^{-10}	8.590×10^{-9}	2.002×10^{-8}

The values of changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined at 30° using standard equations⁹ and are respectively -10.31 KCal/mole, -5.92 KCal/mole, 14.47 Cals/deg/mole for Cu-complex and -11.37 KCal/mole, -29.80 KCal/mole, -60.80 Cals/deg/mole for Ag-complex.

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